

Some considerations on the genera *Boschitestella* and *Orbitestella* (Heterobranchia, Orbitestellidae) with the description of three new species

Algunas consideraciones sobre los géneros *Boschitestella* and *Orbitestella* (Heterobranchia, Orbitestellidae) con la descripción de tres nuevas especies

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ABSTRACT

Species of the family Orbitestellidae (genera *Boschitestella* and *Orbitestella*) are studied from material collected by the authors in the Atlantic (Caribbean and West Africa), Red Sea and some Pacific Ocean (mainly French Polynesia areas). Some comments on their larval shell morphology and distribution are made. Three new species are described.

RESUMEN

Se estudian algunas especies pertenecientes a la familia Orbitestellidae (géneros *Boschitestella* y *Orbitestella*) del material recogido por los autores en el Atlántico (Caribe y África Occidental), Mar Rojo y de algunas zonas del Océano Pacífico (especialmente de la Polinesia Francesa). Se hacen algunos comentarios sobre la morfología de la concha larvaria y la distribución de estas especies. Se describen 3 especies nuevas.

KEY WORDS: *Orbitestella*, *Boschitestella*, taxonomy, new species.

PALABRAS CLAVE: *Orbitestella*, *Boschitestella*, taxonomía, nuevas especies.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Orbitestella* was described by IREDALE (1917: 322, 327-328) who also introduced the family-level name Orbitestellidae. This family is currently placed (BOUCHET ET AL. 2017) in the clade Heterobranchia, with Microdisculidae Iredale & McMichael, 1962 as a synonym. The genus *Boschitestella* Moolenbeek, 1994 is very

similar and therefore is also studied here. Both genera have an extensive distribution worldwide (Table I) and *Orbitestella* is also represented in the fossil record e.g. *O. plicatella* (Cossmann, 1888) and *O. granulata* Lozouet, 1998 from Europe, *O. praehinemoa* Laws, 1939 and *O. praetoreuma* Laws, 1939 from New Zealand. PONDER (1990,

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1998) contributed important information on this family.

The species-level taxonomy of this group is currently not well understood. As an example, *O. bermudezi* has been collected in Cuba, the Cape Verde Islands, São Tomé, Annobon Islands and also in the Red Sea. ROLÁN & RUBIO (1992) described *O. similis* as a new species from the Cape Verde Islands, rather similar morphologically to *O. bermudezi* but considered distinct in view of the large geographical separation from the latter, which had been described as fossil in the Caribbean (AGUAYO & BORRO, 1946). However MOOLENBEEK (1994) considered that both taxa were synonyms, and also the same species as those populations collected in the Gulf of Aqaba, Red Sea, and from the Gulf of Oman. Later, other authors also identified as *O. bermudezi* shells collected in Japan (OKUTANI, 2000), in St Peter and St Paul Islands (LIMA ET AL. 2011), and Bahamas (REDFERN, 2013). This distribution is not easily explained, and maybe will future studies document the reasons for this strange pattern

In many occasions, species belonging to other families have been included in this genus e.g. ARDOVINI & COSSIGNANI, 2004, regarding the West Africa fauna, who included *Orbitestella annuliferum* (Dautzenberg, 1910), *O. calameli* (Jousseume, 1872) or *O. lamy* (Fischer & Nicklès, 1946) which are not Vitrinellidae, not Orbitestellidae. Conversely, many species which clearly belong to *Orbitestella* according to their external shell morphology were described in other genera, e.g. *Homalogyra gemmulata* in TURTON (1932) or *Cyclostrema bastowi* in GATLIFF (1906)

In addition to their extensive distribution, another problem in the study of this group is the very small size (usually < 1 mm), making necessary the use of microscopy, including scanning electron microscopy, for the study of each shell, in order to visualize the microsculpture. Furthermore, these small shells are usually collected from sediments, and

hardly any live-collected specimens are available for anatomical or molecular studies. In comparison with other gastropod genera, the number of the species of the genus *Orbitestella* is not too large, but their shells are very small, similar in shape, sculpture and colour. For all these reasons, we consider that it is almost impossible to make a complete revision. So, we will limit our first work to those species which we could collect or receive material from others collectors. Probably, this first work will be followed by other continuing with the study of other many species which we suppose can be present in many countries and which were not studied yet.

The protoconch (with the only exception of *Boschitestella donaldi*, which comprises two phases) is very small (with about 1/2 -3/4 of whorl after the nucleus). This is usual in species with direct development, therefore expected to have a limited distribution area, and it is very difficult to explain how such species could be so widely distributed. Actually we will follow the actual tendency basing the differences between species in this group only on the shell morphology due the difficult to get alive material for these species with so extremely small size.

We have studied material collected by the first and third authors, as well as material from several expeditions of Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, which are detailed in the material examined and on the museum's website <<https://expeditions.mnhn.fr/>>. These shells were examined with Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM).

Abbreviations

CJL collection of Jean Letourneux
 MHNS Museo de Historia Natural de Santiago de Compostela
 MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid
 MNHN Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris
 ZMA Centre for Biodiversity Naturalis, Leiden

Table I. Distribution of accepted species of *Orbitestella* and *Boschitestella* worldwide.
 Tabla I. Distribución mundial de las especies aceptadas de *Orbitestella* and *Boschitestella*.

Caribbean	<i>Orbitestella bermudezi</i> (Aguayo & Borro, 1946) <i>Orbitestella cubana</i> Rolán & Rubio, 1992	REDFERN, 2013 ROLÁN & RUBIO, 1992
NE Atlantic	<i>Orbitestella dariae</i> (Liuzzi & Zucchi Stofa, 1979) <i>Orbitestella similis</i> Rolán & Rubio, 1992 <i>Orbitestella pruinosa</i> Ortega & Gofas, 2019 <i>Orbitestella sarsi</i> (Bush, 1897)	PONDER, 1990 ROLÁN & RUBIO, 1992, ROLÁN, 2005 ORTEGA & GOFAS, 2019 PONDER, 1990
SW Atlantic	<i>Orbitestella bermudezi</i> (Aguayo & Borro, 1946) <i>Orbitestella patagonica</i> Simone & Zelaya, 2004 <i>Orbitestella ponderi</i> Linse, 2002	LIMA ET AL., 2011 SIMONE & ZELAYA, 2004 LINSE, 2002
South Africa	<i>Orbitestella gemmulata</i> (W. H. Turton, 1932)	TURTON, 1932
Red Sea/Oman Gulf	<i>Orbitestella bermudezi</i> (Aguayo & Borro, 1946) <i>Boschitestella donaldi</i> Moolenbeek, 1994 <i>Boschitestella eloiseae</i> Moolenbeek, 1994	MOOLENBEEK, 1994
Thailand	<i>Boschitestella donaldi</i> Moolenbeek, 1994	MOOLENBEEK, 1994
Japan	<i>Orbitestella bermudezi</i> (Aguayo & Borro, 1946) <i>Orbitestella decorata</i> Laseron, 1954 <i>Orbitestella regina</i> Kay, 1979 <i>Boschitestella eloiseae</i> Moolenbeek, 1994	FUKUDA, 1994: 86, OKUTANI, 2000: 686
Australia	<i>Orbitestella bastowi</i> (Gatliff, 1906) <i>Orbitestella decorata</i> Laseron, 1954 <i>Orbitestella iredalei</i> May, 1920 <i>Orbitestella wareni</i> Ponder, 1990	GATLIFF, 1906, MAY, 1920 PONDER, 1990
New Zealand	<i>Orbitestella hinemoa</i> Mestayer, 1919 <i>Orbitestella toreuma</i> Powell, 1930 <i>Orbitestella parva</i> (Finlay, 1924)	POWELL, 1979
Hawaii	<i>Orbitestella regina</i> Kay, 1979	KAY, 1979
Easter Island	<i>Orbitestella aequicostata</i> Ryaines, 2002	RAINES, 2002

SYSTEMATICS

Family ORBITESTELLIDAE Iredale, 1917

Genus *Boschitestella* Moolenbeek, 1994

Type species: *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994, by original designation

Remarks: The genus *Boschitestella* is characterized by its simple sharp keel on the periphery, and a peculiar structure of its protoconch with two parts: a

small nucleus with a microsculpture of irregular reticulated depressions, followed by another $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, mostly smooth with radial undulations.

Boschitestella donaldi Moolenbeek, 1994 (Figs. 1-3)

Boschitestella donaldi Moolenbeek, 1994: *Apex*, 9 (1): 6.

Type material: Holotype in ZMA (examined on photograph). *Apex*, 9 (1): 6.

Material examined: 120 s: Jordan: Aqaba, 63 s, in sediments, 2-10 m (MNHN). Egypt: 10 s, Hurghada, 10 m (MHNS); 14 s, Hurghada, 30 m (MNCN). South of Madagascar: 1 s, ATIMO VATAE Stn BB03, Lavanono, 25°26.4'S, 45°56.1'E, 14-18 m (MHNS). Mozambique Channel: 1 s, BENTHEDI Stn DR104, edge of Banc de la Zélé, 18-24 m (MNHN); 1 s, BENTHEDI Stn S110, 12°25.6'S, 46°16.2'E, 24 m (MNHN). South Africa: 1 s, Sodwana Bay, Jesser Canyon, U-cave, 125 m (MNHN). Vanuatu: 1 s, MUSORSTOM 8 Stn CP1131-1132, 15°38'S 167°03'/167°04'E, 140-182 m (MNHN); 1 s, BOA0 Stn CP2307, 16°38'S, 167°58'E, 586-646 m (MNHN); 1 s, SANTO 2006 Stn DS99, N. Tutuba I., 15°32'S, 167°17'E, 100-105 m (MNHN). Papua New Guinea: 4 s, MADANG Stn KB20, Kavieng Lagoon, S Coast of Baudisson I., wall with large ledges, 02°45.2'S, 150°41.7'E, 8 m (MNHN). New Caledonia, Loyalty I.: 3 s, Lifou, 17 m (MNHN). Fiji: 1 s, MUSORSTOM 10 Stn CP1369, South of Viti Levu, 18°11'S, 178°23'E, 392-433 m (MNHN); 10 s, Stn DW1381, South of Viti Levu, 18°18'S; 177°54'E, 275-430 m (MNHN); 1 s, Stn DW1345, Bligh Water, 17°15'S, 178°30'E, 660-663 m (MNHN). French Polynesia, Australes: 7 s, Rapa, W Rapa Iti Islet, 24 m (CJL).

Type locality: Sultanate of Oman, Haramal near Muscat, low tide.

Description: (See also MOOLENBEEK, 1994). Shell minute (0.7 to 1.2 mm in diameter) albeit slightly larger than species of *Orbitestella*, depressed, broadly umbilicate, translucent white, and with a prominent peripheral keel. Protoconch about 350 µm in diameter, with two parts: a small nucleus about 100 µm in diameter, with a microsculpture of irregular reticulated depressions, over ¼ whorl; this part followed by another ¾ of whorl, mostly smooth with (Fig. 1G) about 6 radial ridges pointing towards the nucleus, separated by depressed areas. Apparently there is a line which marks the separation between those two parts of the protoconch. Usually the protoconch is light brown in colour. Teleoconch with a sculpture of axial ribs and spirally aligned tubercles, more conspicuous on the adapical part and on the peripheral cord; microsculpture of spiral

threads formed by spirally aligned granules, mainly in the adapical part.

Distribution: According to MOOLENBEEK (1994) the species was found in some places of the Red Sea, Egypt, Gulf of Aqaba, Indonesia and Thailand. We report material from southern Madagascar and from Vanuatu, which is very similar that that already known from Hurghada, Red Sea. This species is very abundant in the Red Sea, Aqaba mainly, and less frequent in other areas. Isolated but very similar shells were collected in southern Madagascar, Vanuatu, New Caledonia, Fiji, Solomon and French Polynesia (new records).

Remarks: The protoconch is very characteristic, as well the periphery with only one keel bearing widely separated nodules, and a dense microsculpture formed by spirally aligned microtubercles.

Genus *Orbitestella* Iredale, 1917

Type species: *Cyclostrema bastowi* Gatliff, 1906, by original designation.

Orbitestella cf. *bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1994) (Figs. 4-6)

Cyclostremiscus bermudezi Aguayo & Borro 1946. *Rev. Soc. Malac.*, 4: 10. [Upper Tertiary, Cuba].
Orbitestella similis Rolán & Rubio, 1992. *La Conchiglia*, 262: 17-19. [Type locality: Teodora Bay, Boavista, Cape Verde Archipelago].

Figure 1. *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994. A-E: shells, 1.13, 0.70, 0.74, 1.08, 1.03 mm, Hurghada, Red Sea, 30 m; F: apex and first teleoconch whorl; G: protoconch.

Figura 1. *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994. A-E: conchas, 1,13, 0,70, 0,74, 1,08, 1,03 mm, Hurgada, Mar Rojo, 30 m; F: ápice y primera vuelta de teleoconcha; G: protoconcha.

Figure 2. *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994. A, B: shell, 1.04 mm, S of Madagascar (MHNS); C, D: protoconchs; E, F: microsculpture and detail.

Figura 2. Boschitestella donaldi Moolenbeek, 1994. A, B: concha, 1,04 mm, S de Madagascar (MHNS); C, D: protoconchas; E, F: microescultura y detalle.

Material examined: 92 s: Cape Verde Is. Holotype of *O. similis* (MNCN); 10 s, Tarrafal, Santiago I., and Pedrinha, Brava I. Annobon I.: 2 s, San Antonio de Palé, 10 m (MHNS). São Tomé I.: 2 s, Praia Azul, 5 m (MHNS). Red Sea: Jordan, Aqaba: 7 s, in sediments, 5-7 m, collected by diving (MHNS). Egypt: Hurghada, 13 s, in sediments, 10-30 m (MNCN). French Polynesia: Marquesas Is.: 1 s, Ua

Figure 3. *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994. A-C: shells, 1.04 mm, Stn CP1307, Vanuatu (MNHN); D: protoconch; E: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 3. *Boschitestella donaldi* Moolenbeek, 1994. A-C: concha, 1,04 mm, Stn CP1307, Vanuatu (MNHN); D: protoconcha; E: detalle de la microescultura.

Pou, Haakuti, Cape Punahu, 9°22.5'S, 140°07'W, 68 m (CJL). Society Is.: 4 s, Tetiaroa, 15 m (MHNS); 10 s, Mehetia, 55 m (MHNS); 8 s, Tahiti, Arue, 20-42 m (MHNS); 7 s, same locality, 22 m (CJL). Australes Is.: 1 s, Rapa, W Rapa Iti Islet, 24 m (CJL); 5 s, same locality (MHNS); 5 s, Rurutu, fringing reef of Vitaria, 1 m (CJL); 2 s, Raivavae, 20 m (CJL). Gambier Is.: 2 s, Tenoko, 23.0739°S, 135.0097°W, 1-3 m (CJL); 3 s, Tarauru Roa, 23.1068°S, 134.8618°W, 1-3 m (CJL); 5 s, Totegegi, 3-5 m (CJL). Tuamotu Is.: 4 s, Fangatau, 1 m (MNCN).

Description: (See also AGUAYO & BORRO, 1994; ROLÁN & RUBIO, 1992 -as *O. similis*-; MOOLENBEEK, 1994). Shell minute (0.6 to 0.9 mm in diameter) depressed, broadly umbilicate, with two peripheral ridges. Sculpture variable,

with axial riblets overrunning the spiral keels and forming a spirally aligned series on knobs on the adapical side.

Protoconch about 130 µm in diameter, with a nucleus of 60 µm and only ½ whorl after the nucleus, smooth except for a

Figure 4. *Orbitestella cf. bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1946). A: shell, 0.61 mm, Aqaba, Jordan, Red Sea, 5 m (MHNS); B, C: shell, 0.60 mm Hurghada, Egypt, Red Sea, 30 m (MHNS); D, E: protoconchs, from a shell of Aqaba and another from Hurghada; F: microsculpture, same shell as B.

Figura 4. *Orbitestella cf. bermudezi* (Aguayo y Borro, 1946). A: concha, 0,61 mm, Aqaba, Jordania, Mar Rojo, 5 m (MHNS); B, C: concha, 0,60 mm Hurghada, Egipto, Mar Rojo, 30 m (MHNS); D, E: protoconcha, ejemplar de Aqaba y otro de Hurghada; F: microescultura, el misma concha que B.

Figure 5. *Orbitestella* cf. *bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1946). A, B: shells, 0.57, 0.56 mm (MHNS), Annobon I.; C-E: shells, 0.57, 0.54, 0.55 mm (MHNS), Praia Azul, São Tomé I.

Figura 5. *Orbitestella* cf. *bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1946). A, B: conchas, 0,57, 0,56 mm (MHNS), Isla de Annobon; C-E: conchas, 0,57, 0,54, 0,55 mm (MHNS), Praia Azul, Isla de Santo Tomé.

broad ridge running from the nucleus to the beginning of the teleoconch.

Distribution: The distribution of this morphospecies is puzzling. It was first described as a fossil of the Cuban Miocene or Pleistocene and later reported as Recent in other West Atlantic and Caribbean islands such as the Bahamas, Puerto Rico, Grenadines (FABER, 1991, REDFERN, 2013). In the Cape Verde Islands, ROLÁN & RUBIO (1992) described it as a new species in consideration to the large distance from the Caribbean type locality. Nevertheless MOOLENBEEK (1994) considered both taxa as synonyms, and further reported the same species from the Gulf of Aqaba, Red Sea and from Gulf of

Oman. OKUTANI (2000: 687) recorded this species from several places in Japan, also showing similar shells. Morphologically, all those are similar to shells we collected in São Tomé and Annobon, off the West African coast (new record), and to the numerous specimens collected in French Polynesia (new record).

Remarks: As the original description is from a fossil material we will refer to the name as "cf." considering that Recent populations are probably conspecific with the fossil one, but with some doubts, and thinking that probably this morphospecies may comprise several different species which we are currently not able to separate with our possibilities of study.

Figure 6. *Orbitestella cf. bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1946). A-D: shells, 0.62, 0.60, 0.66, 0.61 mm, Fangatau, Tuamotu, French Polynesia (CJL); E: protoconch, same shell as A.

Figura 6. *Orbitestella cf. bermudezi* (Aguayo & Borro, 1946). A-D: conchas, 0,62, 0,60, 0,66, 0,61 mm, Fangatau, Tuamotu, Polinesia Francesa (CJL); E: protoconcha, misma concha que A.

Orbitestella cf. bermudezi having a protoconch with a little more than $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl after the nucleus and a diameter of about 130 μm , it must be included among species with a paucispiral protoconch, which are supposed to have a direct development and, in consequence, a short distribution area (BOUCHET, 1987). For this reason it is very surprising that this species is living in all the above mentioned places, and we have no explanation for this presence in widely separated countries. This

species could have an unknown method of dispersion (for example transported by animals or ships) or we may be dealing with several very morphologically similar, but distinct, species. A DNA study could be useful for making clear one of these options.

FUKUDA (1994: 40, pl. 37, fig. 725) presented three large photographs under the name *Orbitestella regina* Kay, 1979, which are very similar to *O. bermudezi*. This taxonomic situation cannot to be resolved at present.

Figure 7. A, B. *Orbitestella* cf. *bermudezi*. A: holotype of *O. similis* Rolán & Rubio, 1992, Teodora Bay, Boavista I., Cape Verde Is. 0.54 mm (MNHN); B: paratype, 0.56 mm (MHNS). C, D. *Orbitestella cubana* Rolán & Rubio, 1992. C: holotype, Cayo Avalos, Canarreos Archipelago, Cuba, 0.65 mm (MNHN); D: paratype, 0.61 mm, same locality (MNHN).

Figura 7. A, B. *Orbitestella* cf. *bermudezi*. A: holotipo de *O. similis* Rolán & Rubio, 1992, Bahía Teodora, Boavista, Archipiélago de Cabo Verde, 0,54 mm (MNHN); B: paratipo, 0,56 mm (MHNS). C, D. *Orbitestella cubana* Rolán & Rubio, 1992. C: holotipo, Cayo Avalos, Archipiélago de los Canarreos, Cuba, 0,65 mm (MNHN); D: paratipo, 0,61 mm, misma localidad (MNHN).

Orbitestella cubana Rolán & Rubio, 1992 (Fig. 7C, D)

Orbitestella cubana Rolán & Rubio, 1992. *La Conchiglia*, 23 (262): 17-20. [Type locality: Cayo Avalos, Canarreos Archipelago, Cuba].

Material examined: Cuba: Holotype of *O. cubana* (MNCN); 10 s, Cayo Avalos, Canarreos, Cuba, and 1 s in Baracoa, Cuba.

Remarks: The shells of this species studied from Cuba were morphologically different from *O. bermudezi*, having numerous axial oblique ribs and fewer nodules (expressed only on the first adapical whorl) while in the abapical part the nodules are placed very close to the umbilical suture and not further towards the middle of the whorl. These

two species may be compared on Figure 7. Shells of *Orbitestella bermudezi* from Abaco, Bahamas figured by REDFERN (2013: 228, figures 635A, 635B) are similar to those so identified herein, but his figure 635C has a morphology approaching *O. cubana*, with more numerous axial ribs and less distinct knobs on the spire.

Orbitestella cf. *decorata* Laseron, 1954 (Fig. 8)

Orbitestella decorata Laseron, 1954. [Port Stephens, NSW, southwards to Mallacoota, Victoria, Australia]

Material examined: 68 s: Vanuatu: 6 s, MUSORSTOM 8: Stn DW1065, 16°16'S-167°21'E, 360-419 m. French Polynesia, Marquesas Is.: 2 s, Ua pou, Haakuti, Cape Punahu, 9°22.5'S, 140°07'W, 68 m (MHNS). Gambier Is.: 1 s, Mangareva, Rikitea, 1 m (CJL); 12 s, same locality (MNHN); 1 s, Totegegi, 3-5 m (MHNS). Society Is.: 13 s, Mehetia, 55 m (CJL); 8 s, Tahiti, Arue, 5 m (MHNS); 7 s, same locality, 1 m (CJL). Tuamotu Is.: 2 s, Rangiroa, passe of Tiputa, 100 m (MNCN); 13 s, Makemo, Pohue, 63-83 m (MNHN); 3 s, Katiu, reef, 1 m (CJL).

Description: Shell minute (up to 0.8 mm), discoid, translucent, shiny, solid. Protoconch about 130 μ m in diameter, with a nucleus of 60 μ m and only $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl after the nucleus; with two spiral cords at the beginning, one very close to the suture and the other one running across the middle of the protoconch and abutting on the suture. Teleoconch with a little more than 2 whorls, strongly sculptured, with somewhat undulating axial ribs which are more elevated and wider in the part near the suture, then reduced along a spiral depression, and again more elevated towards the periphery. There are between 30-35 on the last whorl and 16-19 on the first one. Sometimes, at the end of the last whorl the axial ribs are more numerous and less prominent. At the periphery, there are two prominent spiral cords, the upper one with knobs at the termination of the axial ribs and the lower one with smaller knobs; these cords are separated by a depression in which fine oblique axial lines can be seen. On the abapical side, between the lower peripheral cord and the umbilicus, there are smooth ribs, similar in number to the adapical part. Umbilicus wide, showing the previous whorls. Aperture rounded but indented by the termination of the interspaces.

Distribution: This species is reported from several areas as Australia, Japan, and herein from Vanuatu and from Marquesas Is., French Polynesia (new records). It is probably present in many other areas.

Remarks: We have some doubts about the identification of this species

with the taxon *O. decorata*. The images in PONDER (1998) show a shell with similar sculpture, but the protoconch has a wide cord, which in our material seems to be smaller. Conversely, on the images presented by OKUTANI (2000) the shell has more sculpture but the protoconch seems to be similar to ours from French Polynesia. Anyway, provisionally we will consider our material included in this taxon.

The present species, when juvenile, can show only one more developed spiral cord on the periphery (see Figure 8F) suggesting a different species. In the following whorls, the external cord bounding the adapical surface becomes similar to the abapical one, as can be seen in Fig. 8E.

Orbitestella bermudezi (Aguayo & Borro, 1946) is similar in shape, but has less axial ribs, about 14 on the first whorl and about 17-20 on the last whorl, and the thickened part of the ribs forms an elevation in the middle of the spire whorls. The sculpture includes also some spiral cordlets, not present in *O. decorata*. The protoconch is similar in size but with a wide cord which runs from the nucleus to the end of the protoconch, not abutting against the suture. The periphery is flat or very slightly convex, not channelled, and has a sculpture of fine, prosocline, slightly undulating axial riblets with about 10-12 very fine spiral lines in the interspaces.

Orbitestella regina Kay, 1979 has a similar shell with two peripheral cords, but the cord which crosses the protoconch seems to be larger (KAY, 1979, fig. 32).

Figure 8. *Orbitestella* cf. *decorata* Laseron, 1954. A-E: shells, from French Polynesia, Gambier Is., 1 m (MNHN), 0.60, 0.66, 0.76, 0.7, 0.8 mm (MNHN); F: juvenile shell apparently with only one peripheral cord, 0.6 mm, same locality (MNHN); G: protoconch, same shell as A.

Figura 8. Orbitestella cf. *decorata* Laseron, 1954. A-E: conchas de Polinesia Francesa, Islas Gambier, 1 m (MNHN), 0,60, 0,66, 0,76, 0,7, 0,8 mm; F: concha juvenil aparentemente con solo un cordón periférico, 0,6 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); G: protoconcha, misma concha que A.

Orbitestella radiata n. sp. (Figure 9A-F, 10A-H, 11A-G)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 9A) MNHN-IM-2000-35190, and 3 paratypes (Figs. 9B-D) MNHN-IM-2000-35191; other paratypes: 4 s in MNCN (15.05/200083); 3 s in MHNS (); 2 s in CJL; 1 in CFR.

Other material examined: 225 s: French Polynesia, Society Is.: 12 s, Tetiaroa, 15 m (MHNS); Marquesas Is.: about 180 s, Ua Pou (Haakuti) Cape Punahu, 68 m (type material); Tuamotu Isl.: 30 s, Pinaki, 1 m; Australes Is.: 3 s, Rapa, W Rapa Iti islet, 24 m.

Type locality: Marquesas Is., Ua Pou, Haakuti, Cape Punahu, 9°22.5'S, 140°07'W, 68 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin whorl *radiatus*, *a, um* alluding the axial radiating sculpture.

Description: Shell minute (up to 0.77 mm), discoid, white, hardly translucent, shiny, fragile. Protoconch about 130 μ m in diameter, with a nucleus of 60 μ m and a little more than ½ whorl after the nucleus, totally smooth. Teleoconch with about 2 whorls or a little less, strongly sculptured, with a prominent keel on the periphery from which the upper and lower surface form an obtuse angle, a blunt ridge along the middle part of the spire whorl and another one surrounding the abapical surface. The suture is deep, running just above the peripheral keel of the previous whorl. The sculpture consists of somewhat undulating, narrow axial riblets, between 25-35 on the first whorl and 50-80 on the last one. The riblets are raised where they cross over the elevation of the spire, without forming any tubercles or nodules in this area; they continue down to the prominent peripheral keel, and fade out towards the abapical part in many shells. Sometimes, at the end of the last whorl, the axial ribs are more numerous and less prominent.

All the surface between the cords are smooth or with a variable number of spiral threads over the entire shell, or sometimes only on the angle of the abapical part of the last whorl. Umbilicus wide, showing the previous whorls. Aperture rounded, tending to polygonal due to the termination of the spiral keels.

The holotype is 0.61 x 0.3 mm. Some paratypes are a little larger.

Variations: In the study of a large amount of shells, we were able to separate some groups in the basis of a few characters in the periphery and microsculpture, being most of the others perfectly similar. We consider these

characters within the specific variation but worth to mention them:

- Form n° 1: with a periphery almost smooth, with attenuated axial riblets and without spiral cordlets. This form corresponds to the holotype and to specimens illustrated on Figs. 9C and 9G.

- Form n° 2: with almost no axial sculpture on the periphery but with evident spiral lines more appreciable all over the shell (see Fig. 10).

-Form n° 3: this form presents in apical view the same aspect than the previous ones, but on the periphery there are numerous axial riblets (see Figs. 11B-C) which are prosocline and slightly undulated.

Distribution: Known from French Polynesia, Society, Marquesas, Tuamotu and Australes Islands.

Remarks: *Boschitestella donaldi* is a little larger; the sculpture forms prominent nodules in the middle of the adapical part of the whorls; it also has a prominent peripheral keel bearing distinct, widely separated nodules, and situated towards the lower part of the periphery instead of towards the upper part; the protoconch is different, with definite radial ridges.

Orbitestella bermudezi is very different: the protoconch has a wide spiral cord; the teleoconch has very well marked nodules over all the shell; the axial ribs are less numerous. *Orbitestella cubana* has a protoconch similar to that of *O. bermudezi*, but in the end of the teleoconch with a much denser axial sculpture, yet not as dense as in *O. radiata*. On the base, the nodules are situated more internally, closer to the umbilicus.

O. decorata has a double spiral cord on the periphery and also its protoconch

Figure 9. *Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A: holotype, 0.61 mm, Ua Pou, Haakuti, Marquesas (MNHN); B-D: paratypes, 0.71, 0.7, 0.72 mm, same locality (MNHN); E, F: protoconchs of the holotype and of a paratype; G: detail of the periphery, same shell as C.

A-F *Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A: holotipo, 0,61 mm, Ua Pou, Haakuti, Marquesas (MNHN); B-D: paratipos, 0,71, 0,7, 0,72 mm, misma localidad (MNHN); E, F: protoconchas del holotipo y de un paratipo; G: detalle de la periferia, misma concha que C.

Figure 10. *Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A-E: shells, 0.77, 0.76, 0.73, 0.71 mm, French Polynesia, Tuamotu, Pinaki, 1 m (MNHN); F: protoconch, same shell as C; G, H: detail of the microsculpture. *Figura 10. Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A-E: conchas, 0,77, 0,76, 0,73, 0,71 mm, Polinesia Francesa, Tuamotu, Pinaki, 1 m (MNHN); F: protoconcha, misma concha que C; G, H: detall de la microscultura.

has a spiral sculpture. The axial folds are less numerous and are swollen along the central part of the spire whorl.

Differences with other species described in the present work are mentioned under the relevant species.

Figure 11. *Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A-E: shells, 0.70, 0.71, 0.68, 0.66, 0.50 mm, French Polynesia, Tuamotu, Pinaki, about 1 m (MNHN); F, G: protoconch and detail.

Figura 11. *Orbitestella radiata* n. sp. A-E: conchas, 0,70, 0,71, 0,68, 0,66, 0,50 mm, Polinesia Francesa, Tuamotu, Pinaki, alrededor de 1 m (MNHN); F, G: protoconcha y detalle.

Orbitestella furtiva n. sp. (Fig. 12)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 12A) MNHN-IM-2000-35192 from SALOMON 2 DW 1762, and a paratype (Fig. 12B) lost during the study.

Material examined: 2 s, from the type locality.

Type locality: Solomon Is., Rendova, 8°38'S, 157°22'E, 195-197 m.

Etymology: The specific name derives from the Latin *furtivus, a, um*, which means "hidden" alluding to the difficulty to find it and the scarce material obtained.

Description: Shell minute (0.77 mm), discoid, white, hardly translucent, shiny, solid. Protoconch about 160 μ m in diameter, with a nucleus of 70 μ m and almost $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl after the nucleus, smooth except for some minute tubercles at the beginning. Teleoconch with about 2 whorls, strongly sculptured, with a prominent keel on the periphery, a blunt ridge along the middle part of the spire whorl and another one surrounding the abapical surface. The suture is deep, running on the peripheral keel of the previous whorl. The sculpture consists of somewhat undulating, narrow axial riblets, about 16 on the first whorl and up to 60 on the last one, much narrower than the interspaces. The riblets cross over the ridge of the spire, and on the second whorl they are narrower, undulating and a little irregular; on the last half whorl the axial ribs are more numerous and less prominent. All the surface is covered by very fine, marked and continuous spiral threads, narrower than their interspaces, more numerous and dense above the suture and on the periphery. These are crossed by fine, dense axial threads, more conspicuous in the beginning of the spire. On the abapical surface, there are very numerous fine axial riblets (up to 70) crossed by spiral threads more attenuated than those on the spire. Umbilicus wide, showing the previous whorls. Aperture rounded, tending to polygonal due to the termination of the spiral keels.

Dimensions: The holotype is 0.77 mm in diameter x 0.24 mm in height.

Distribution: Only known in Solomon Island.

Remarks: By its almost smooth protoconch this species is easily separated from *O. bermudezi* and *O. decorata* which have a protoconch clearly sculptured.

O. furtiva spec. nov. has some similarity with *Boschitestella eloiseae* Moolenbeek, 1994 but the latter species has (from the scale bar in the figure of the original description) a protoconch of about 200 μ m and a nucleus of 100 μ m (instead of 160 and 70 of the present species), and in this protoconch there are two parts, the first one with an irregular microsculpture, and the second with broad axial folds, whereas the protoconch of *O. furtiva* n. sp. is smooth. *Orbitestella furtiva* has some nodules and somewhat fewer axial ribs at the beginning of the teleoconch.

Boschitestella donaldi is larger, the protoconch is different with brown colour and two phases, with different microsculptures.

Orbitestella radiata n.sp. has the peripheral keel situated towards its higher part, whereas in *O. furtiva* it is median. The first whorl has very few axial riblets, whereas the abapical part has a much denser axial sculpture. The spiral sculpture of *O. furtiva* is scarce except near the suture.

Orbitestella nova n. sp. (Fig. 13)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 13A) from PAPUA NIUGINI Stn PD10, MNHN-IM-2000-35193.

Material examined: Only the holotype.

Type locality: Papua New Guinea, W. Kranket I., 05°11.7'S - 145°48.8'E, 16-28 m.

Etymology: The specific name is from the Latin *novus, a, um* alluding that is the last species found after the examination of a lot of samples.

Figure 12. *Orbitestella furtiva* n. sp. A: holotype, 0.77 mm, Solomon I., Rendova, 195 m (MNHN-IM-2000-35192); B, C: paratype, 0.85 mm, from the same locality (MNHN); D, E: protoconch and detail from the holotype; F, G: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 12. *Orbitestella furtiva* n. sp. A: holotipo, 0,77 mm, Islas Salomón, Rendova, 195 m (MNHN); B, C: paratipo, 0,85 mm, de la misma localidad (MNHN); D, E: protoconcha y detalle del holotipo; F, G: detalle de la microescultura.

Description: Shell minute (1 mm), discoid, white, hardly translucent, shiny, solid. Protoconch about 150 µm in diameter, with a nucleus of 60 µm and almost one whorl after the nucleus, totally smooth. Teleoconch with about 2

whorls, strongly sculptured, with a prominent keel on the periphery, a blunt ridge along the middle part of the spire whorl and another one surrounding the abapical surface. The external part of the whorl forms a depression

Figure 13. *Orbitestella nova* n. sp. A-C: holotype, 1.0 mm in diameter, Papua New Guinea, 25 m, (MNHN); D, E: protoconch and detail.

Figura 13. *A-E. Orbitestella nova spec. nov. A-C: holotipo, 1,0 mm de diámetro, Papua Nueva Guinea, 25 m, (MNHN); D, E: protoconcha y detalle.*

above and below the peripheral keel. The suture is deep, running just above the peripheral keel of the previous whorl. The sculpture on the adapical part consists of axial ribs, much narrower than the interspaces, which run over the adapical ridge and terminate with projecting knobs on the peripheral keel; there are about 16 on the first whorl and about 29 on the last one. At the intersection with the ridge on the spire whorls, the ribs form a marked angle and short elevated knobs, particularly prominent on the first teleoconch whorl. On the abapical part, there are

about 46 axial ribs, one out of two continued from the peripheral keel and the others intercalated; these form a marked angle at their intersection with the abapical ridge and are continued into the broad umbilicus. The entire surface between ribs is covered by very fine tubercles which are aligned axially and spirally. The umbilicus is wide, showing the previous whorls. Aperture rounded but with some depressions produced by the end of the interspaces of the cords. Aperture rounded, tending to polygonal due to the termination of the spiral keels.

Dimensions: the holotype is 1.0 mm in diameter x 0.29 mm in height.

Distribution: Only known from Papua New Guinea.

Remarks: The shell of *Orbitestella nova* n. sp. is very characteristic and can be differentiated from the other known species:

O. bermudezi and *O. decorata* do not have a single peripheral keel, have a sculpture with more conspicuous nodules, and have a prominent spiral cord on the protoconch.

Boschitestella donaldi Moolenbeek, 1994 has a very different protoconch. *Boschitestella eloisae* Moolenbeek, 1994 has a protoconch of about 200 μm (instead of 150 μm) and a nucleus of 100 μm (instead of 60 μm), and have a different microsculpture with the granules

not clearly aligned as in *O. nova*, and besides has 19 instead of 15 axial ribs on the first teleoconch whorl.

Orbitestella radiata has much more numerous axial ribs on the adapical area, while the abapical part has very scarce sculpture; the periphery has the prominent cord placed higher towards the adapical part and with numerous riblets crossing it.

O. furtiva is the most similar species but differs in the number of the axial ribs, separated and less numerous on the last whorl of *O. nova*, also less marked and more numerous on the abapical part. The protoconch of *O. furtiva* is slightly larger but does not exceed $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, whereas it has almost one whorl in *O. nova*.

Orbitestella sp. (Fig. 14)

Type material: The shell examined (Figs. 14A-C) was to be the holotype, unfortunately it was broken during the photographic study.

Material examined: Red Sea, Egypt, Hurghada, at 20-30 m.

Description: Shell minute (1.1 mm), discoid, white, scarcely translucent, shiny, fragile.

Protoconch about 200 μm in diameter, with a nucleus of 80 μm and almost $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl after the nucleus, totally smooth.

Teleoconch with about 2 whorls, strongly sculptured, with a prominent keel on the periphery and a blunt ridge along the middle part of the spire whorl, attenuated on the last whorl. The suture is deep, running just above the peripheral keel of the previous whorl.

The sculpture consists of narrow axial ribs which cross over the ridge in the middle of the whorl, about 42-47 on the first whorl and 60-63 on the second. There is almost no apparent spiral sculpture. Umbilicus wide, showing the previous whorls. Aperture rounded. Aperture rounded, tending to polygonal due to the termination of the spiral keels.

The shell studied was 1.1 mm in diameter x 0.55 mm in height.

Distribution: Only known from Hurghada.

Remarks: Only one shell of this species was found in Hurghada, but it is clearly different from the other species found in the Red Sea. Because the only shell obtained was broken during study, we decided not to name it, but still find appropriate to describe and illustrate it. The most important difference is the much higher number of axial riblets on the last whorl (up to 63) only comparable with *O. radiata* n. sp. (which can reach up to 60). A further difference is that on the periphery, the riblets of *O. radiata* are prosocline while in the present species they are orthocline and faded. The sizes of the protoconchs are different (protoconch diameter 150 μm and the nucleus 50 μm in *O. radiata* against 200 and 80 μm here). *Orbitestella radiata* has a ridge on the abapical surface which not is present in *Orbitestella* sp., which conversely has a ridge bounding the umbilicus. The latter species lacks also tubercles on the periphery.

Figure 14. *Orbitestella* sp. A-C: shell (broken during study), 1.1 mm, Hurgada, 30 m (MNHN); D: protoconch; E, F: detail of the microsculpture.

Figura 14. A-F *Orbitestella* sp. A-C: concha (rota durante su estudio), 1,1 mm, Hurgada, 30 m (MNHN); D: protoconcha; E, F: detalle de la microescultura.

DISCUSSION

More than 650 shells have been examined so far and we have made more than 160 photographs to the SEM

for this study. The *Orbitestella* group was very difficult to study, not only because of small size (normally not exceeding 1

mm, most closer to 0.6 mm) which makes difficult the comparison of sculpture even with a good magnifying glass, or a stereomicroscope. In addition, they lack colour, being transparent (whitish when they lost transparency). The scanning electron microscope micrographs (SEM) are the ideal tool for their study, but requires immense work when it comes to compare hundreds of shells.

Another problem that causes difficulties for species comparison and separation is the numerous examples of populations scattered on islands which, usually, have a high number of endemic species. A number of species, despite their paucispiral protoconch (1/2 to 3/4 of whorl after the nucleus) were found in very distant places. These would be expected to have a low capacity for dispersion, but surprisingly exist in places very far apart. We are not really sure if this abnormal presence may be due to human mediation which could have facilitated their dispersion (e.g. in passive transport, as in ship hulls, transported rocks or sand, through seafood trade which has increased significantly in recent years). However it is striking that Europe, which supports the highest maritime traffic, is so far free of the presence of species of these genera, except the Mediterranean *O. dariae*.

A further possibility, which we can not rule out, is that we are comparing species of similar morphology, but which may be indeed reproductively isolated. The collection of live material

and study of genetic sequences could respond to these doubts. Much more material from many places, mainly provided by the MNHN of Paris, is currently available for study and we hope that further work clarifies the complex taxonomy of this group.

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